

The Role of Cognitive Biases in Asynchronous Online Discussions

Dominik Wyss

University of Lucerne
University of Stuttgart

Abstract

Are citizens capable to form attitudes as a result of unprejudiced examination of reasons? By pooling data from four field experiments, the study assesses the effects of cognitive biases on attitude extremity in asynchronous discussions. The focus lies on two cognitive biases, namely a confirmation bias (preference to read attitudinal congruent arguments) and a disconfirmation bias (tendency to seek flaws only in incongruent arguments). The study finds (1) high prevalence of cognitive biases, (2) but without effect on attitude extremity, instead (3) with a strong correlation with forum activity. The findings give succor for the argumentative theory of reasoning proposed by Hugo Mercier and Helene Landemore in stating that discussion participants are biased in how they react to arguments, but not so biased that discussion reinforces their attitudes. Moreover, the individual's pursuit to defend initially hold attitudes seems to be an essential impetus for discussion engagement.

Introduction

An intriguing question in democratic theory is whether citizens are capable to form attitudes as a result of unprejudiced examination of reasons. To this question, motivated reasoning theory offers a pessimistic answer in claiming that people process political information in an extremely biased way, mostly in order to defend and maintain previously obtained attitudes and less to find attitudes that are accurate (Taber, Cann, & Kucsova, 2009; Taber & Lodge, 2006). The theory predicts that citizens tend to seek and readily accept evidence that is ideologically congruent (a confirmation bias) and spend a lot of cognitive effort in seeking weaknesses of incongruent evidence (a disconfirmation bias). Motivated reasoning theory then predicts deleterious consequences of such cognitive biases, foremost that initially held attitudes tend to self-enforce and thus sustain, rather than bridge, prevailing shifts in society (Flynn, Reifler, & Nyhan, 2016; Richey, 2012).

A much more positive view on cognitive biases is offered by the argumentative theory of reasoning, at least when reasoning happens in groups (Mercier & Landemore, 2012; Mercier & Sperber, 2011). In group discussions, the individual blind spots caused by cognitive biases become visible for interlocutors. Due to the revealing of own blind spots biases, group members become aware that their attitudes are not to defend by rational arguments what ultimately could trigger an attitude shift towards a more defensible stance (Mercier & Sperber, 2011). While the confirmation bias hinders cognitive activities for autonomous reasoners, it increases cognitive activities in the face of feedback loops, as everyone perceives a need to defend its position. Under feedback loops, participants justify their views, seek and bring in more arguments supporting their position, put under strong scrutiny the vantage points of fellow discussants, and—assuming interlocutors do the same—become aware of flaws in their own viewpoints (Mercier & Landemore, 2012, p. 246).

There is a need to investigate whether and under which conditions group discussions alleviate deleterious effects of cognitive biases. This need is addressed by the current study, which focuses on the context of asynchronous online forums. The study investigates the role played by cognitive biases on a pooled dataset of four asynchronous discussions that took place in Switzerland and Germany. While the four online discussions were conducted on the same platform, they differ in following aspects: First, one online discussion was conducted as a publicly accessible discussion during the campaign phase of a Swiss initiative, while the other discussions were conducted as a field experiment with preselected and randomized participants. One of these discussions took place in Germany and was about citizens' attitudes towards democratic governance models, whereas the other discussions were about a highly conflictive migration topic, namely a Swiss initiative asking for the expulsion of criminal migrants. Finally, three of the four discussions featured an artificial facilitator which was in charge to facilitate the argumentative exchange among participants (reference omitted).

By analyzing these four online discussions a broad pattern of information processing and attitude formation processes can be observed, which allows to assess whether cognitive biases

are relevant, and whether they affect attitudes in a way that they shift towards extremes. One methodical advantage of using asynchronous forums is that they allow to track confirmation and disconfirmation bias accurately by focusing on the available log files. While most conventional research in this topic relies on lab-experiments, this approach allows to assess effects of cognitive biases in real-life online discussions. Second, on a continuum between face-to-face discussions and individual reasoning, asynchronous forums stand for an intermediary form of reasoning, in which citizens interact with interlocutors, but interaction is substantially restricted. Where exactly on the continuum online discussions are situated hinges on the concrete forum design. Design features influence people's need to hold on their prior attitudes, the perceived need to justify them by rational arguments or the pace of the argumentative exchange. The advantage here is that by manipulating design features, researchers can obtain a closer look on antecedents, prevalence, and consequences of cognitive biases.

The article is divided in four sections. I start with a theoretical discussion of cognitive effects and their effects on attitude extremity. Here, I also discuss how asynchronous online discussions might interfere. Second, I present the methodical procedure, introduce the data, and specify the hypotheses. Third, I present the results of several multilevel models and some bivariate statistics, which assess on one side the prevalence of cognitive biases during forum discussion and on the other side, their effect on attitude extremity. And fourth, I discuss the findings and elaborate how it connects to motivated reasoning theory and argumentative theory of reasoning.

A Theoretical Overview

The phenomenon in the literature known as motivated reasoning is a prominent psychological account of how people process political information (Mutz, 2009). A basic premise is that information processing is more often aimed at directional goals such as the defense and maintenance of previously obtained extant values and identities rather than accuracy goals such as forming attitudes that are as accurate as possible (Slothuus & de Vreese, 2010). Motivated reasoning “occurs at every step of information processing, from setting goals, to gathering and evaluating evidence from the outside or from memory, to constructing inferences and judgments” (Mendelberg, 2002). Consequently, motivated reasoners have at their disposal a broad set of innovative cognitive strategies that all serve to find and interpret evidence to support as well as to cope with information that conflicts with their view (Kunda, 1990). The strategies are, for instance, biased information search, biased evaluation of information, biased assimilation, and identity-protective cognition.

An underlying motive for motivated reasoning is people's inclination to conceal (from others and from one selves) that attitudes are not created by rational considerations but by stereotypes, instinct, or heuristics (Bodenhausen & Macrae, 1998, p. 22f). An important part of motivated reasoning is genuine self-deception, in which people with entrenched attitudes maintain an “illusion of objectivity” (Pyszczynski and Greenberg 1987). People are good in convincing

themselves that their reasoning processes are thorough and impartial, even when they are not (Bodenhausen & Macrae, 1998, p. 22f).

Political scientists take motivated reasoning seriously due to its potential to hamper accommodation and to intensify prevailing cleavages in society (Flynn et al., 2016; Richey, 2012). They warn against a polarization effect triggered by the cognitive biases, namely that previously formed attitudes shift towards the extremes after being confronted with arguments (Taber et al., 2009; Taber & Lodge, 2006). Concurrently, participants become overconfident about the accuracy of their attitudes (Koriat, Lichtenstein, & Fischhoff, 1980). Due to mechanisms related to motivated reasoning theory, the provision of arguments might even trigger a “boomerang” or “backfire” effect” such that in the view of negatively valenced information people become more supportive of a preferred candidate (Brendan Nyhan & Jason Reifler, 2010; Hart & Nisbet, 2012; Redlawsk, 2002).

Motivated Reasoning in Collective Contexts

Theorists agree that motivated reasoning occurs in both individual and collective contexts. Scholars even warn that discussion groups might amplify individual biases (Levendusky, Druckman, & McLain, 2016; Mendelberg, 2002, p. 169). Collective context might exacerbate motivated reasoning propensity due to the group’s ability to heighten individuals’ “defense motivation” (Mendelberg, 2002, p. 169). More pronounced than in individual context, people try to be ready to meet the challenges of others (Mercier & Landemore, 2012; Tetlock, Skitka, & Boettger, 1989). This chimes well with the results of an experiment conducted by Chen and colleagues. The authors found that people engage more seriously in motivated reasoning when they have the opportunity to counter-argue information provided by the organizers of the experiment. When no such opportunity is given, the extent to which people engage in motivated reasoning is lower (Chen, Housholder, Ksiazkiewicz, & Sheagley, 2014). Because motivated reasoning is accentuated in group discussions and might have deleterious effects on the rationality, reasonableness and epistemic correctness of the outcomes, theorists consider it as a fundamental challenge to deliberative democracy (Mendelberg, 2002; Morrell, 2014; Moscrop, 2015).

However, although motivated reasoning might take an enhanced role in group discussions, it does not mean that it necessarily contradicts accuracy goals. In the context of their argumentative theory of reasoning, Hugo Mercier and Helene Landemore stress that the aforementioned cognitive biases in collective contexts are not flaws but can represent “evolutionary” advantages. When individuals attempt to explain policy positions to their fellows and engage in mutual justification, they are incentivized to highlight the validity of their attitudes based on universally intelligible reasons, while concurrently seeking flaws in dissenting arguments (Mercier & Landemore, 2012; Mercier & Sperber, 2011). If these activities are performed iteratively and mutually, cognitive biases will thus lead to an efficient division of cognitive labor where proponents of various conclusions put forward their own

arguments, which then end up in “epistemically sounder beliefs” (Mercier & Landemore, 2012, p. 248).

Yet, the argumentative theory of reasoning rests on several related assumptions. First, attitudes represented in discussion groups must be adequately diverse, so that the blind spots produced by cognitive biases are not overlapping (Landemore & Mercier, 2012). Moreover, the group discussion must ensure that argumentative exchanges (respectively “feedback loops”) are comprehensively and efficiently organized (p. 918). By the same token, the interlocutors must perceive a need to explain and justify their preferences and underlying reasons (Gutmann & Thompson, 1996). A facilitating condition is also when “arational receptivity” prevails—a state in which individuals are open to publicly questioning and discussing their affective disposition (Moscrop, 2015, p. 16). These conditions contribute that interlocutors make each other aware of the individual cognitive biases and thus occasionally provoke participants to respond with rational updating of their attitudes (Mercier & Landemore, 2012; Morrell, 2014; Moscrop, 2015).

While these conditions seem to be demanding, we know from many deliberative mini-publics that polarized attitudes is not a likely outcome; instead, participant’s attitudes often become more moderate or remain stable (Gastil, Black, & Moscovitz, 2008; Gerber et al., 2014; Kogan & Wallach, 1966; Luskin, Fishkin, & Hahn, 2007; Luskin, O’Flynn, Fishkin, & Russell, 2014; Vinokur & Burnstein, 1978). Even experimental studies with homogenous discussion groups (a condition highly favorable for motivated reasoners, since incongruent arguments are underprovided) could not find any polarization tendencies (Grönlund, Herne, & Setälä, 2015; Karpowitz, Raphael, & Hammond, 2009). And some results from online experiments (mostly synchronous chats) do not indicate an increased propensity for attitude polarization either (Iyengar, Luskin, & Fishkin, 2003; Muhlberger, 2013; similar Triantafillidou, Yannas, Lappas, & Kleftodimos, 2015). Yet, at this stage of research, it remains largely unexplored whether and with which consequences motivated reasoning has in asynchronous online discussions, a recent innovation in the practice of involving citizens in public dialogue.

A note on asynchronous forums

Asynchronous discussions offer some unique characteristics that affect the role played by cognitive biases. A first relevant characteristic is the large amount of postings in online forums, creating a high potential for selective exposure (Sunstein, 2009). In such environments, it is easy for participants to find support for that what they believe. Often, the amount of available information exceeds the reception capacity of individuals, and requires filter mechanisms reinforcing selective exposure (Buder, Schwind, Rudat, & Bodemer, 2015). In this respect, online environments and asynchronous forums can be considered as favorable for motivated reasoning as they allow users to self-select information and gravitate toward congenial information sources and attitudes (Shapiro, 2013).

However, there might be also some inhibiting effects. In more or less anonymous environments with low social cues (particularly if users are only weakly associated with their positions) anonymity may cause them to be more ready to give up their positions (Bosio, Graffigna, & Lozza, 2008, p. 199; Sia, Tan, & Wei, 2002). Similar, motivated reasoning also relates to social and moral norms, in particular accountability (Gutmann & Thompson, 1996; Tetlock et al., 1989). In absence of social norms, might cause a lack of need to find consistent positions backed up by rational arguments—a potential driver for motivated reasoning. This becomes relevant as empirical and theoretical literature stress that computer-mediated communication—in particular under anonymity—tend to underprovide social and moral norms (Bicchieri & Lev-On, 2007, p. 156; Dahlberg, 2001, p. 10; Garnham, 1993; Janssen & Kies, 2005, p. 321; Streck, 2013, p. 46). In sum, these considerations suggest that motivated reasoning in online discussions is prevalent, although to a lower extent than in face-to-face discussions.

Procedure

While motivated reasoning theory encompasses a large variety of mechanisms, the focus of this study lies on both disconfirmation and confirmation bias (Molden & Higgins, 2005; Taber & Lodge, 2006). The first describes the tendency that people encountering attitudinal incongruent information engage in critically thinking, whereas, when evidence is consistent with their theories, these same people remain passive (Edwards & Smith, 1996; Molden & Higgins, 2005). Furthermore, because cognitive resources spend for scrutinizing incongruent arguments is much larger than for scrutinizing congruent arguments, participants find more flaws in the incongruent arguments. These expectations are summarized in the first two hypotheses:

H1 I predict a disconfirmation bias, namely that participant's reflection of arguments is biased such that they invest more time on attitudinal incongruent information (time bias).

H2 The extra time spend at incongruent information is used for critical examination and, thus, negatively affects argument evaluation (effect of time bias on evaluation bias).

The second mechanism, confirmation bias or selective exposure (Hart et al. 2009), is allegedly one of the most studied biases in psychology (Mercier & Sperber, 2011, p. 63). Consequently, it is also well addressed in the context of online information exposure (Garrett, 2009; T. J. Johnson, Zhang, & Bichard, 2011; Thomas J. Johnson & Kaye, 2013; Knobloch-Westerwick, 2012). Typically, confirmation bias is linked to the seeking or interpreting of evidence in ways that are partial to existing beliefs, expectations, or a hypothesis in hand (Nickerson, 1998). From the perspective of motivated reasoning, confirmation bias produces search patterns preferring information that is attitudinal congruent (Chen et al., 2014). The confirmation bias creates a false perception that most available arguments support the own views and thus lowers the chance that people seek out for arguments that contradict one's prior attitude. This leads to the third hypothesis.

H3 Motivated reasoning theory presupposes a confirmation bias, namely that participants tend to seek congruent arguments and avoid incongruent ones (reading bias).

Finally, motivated reasoning also makes predictions about attitude shifts. The expectation is that disconfirmation as well as the confirmation bias move participants' attitudes towards the extremes.

H4 Participants with strong individual cognitive biases are expected to shift their attitudes towards positions that are more extreme (effect of time and reading bias on attitude extremity).

Measuring Motivated Reasoning

For assessing the hypothesis, three bias measurements are calculated. The first one is the time bias, which measures the difference of the reflection time spent on counter and pro arguments (Formula 1).¹ Reflection time is operationalized as the logarithmized time passed between when participants expand a posting and when they rate it. For motivated reasoners, I expect a positive correlation between the time bias and participant's prior attitudes, meaning when they are in favor of the topic under discussion, they spend more time reflecting counter arguments.

Formula 1: time bias

$$time\ bias = \sum_{i=0}^{N_c} \frac{\log(t_{i,c})}{N_c} - \sum_{j=0}^{N_p} \frac{\log(t_{j,p})}{N_p}$$

t: reflection time for each argument

p: pro arguments (Arguments that supports the issue under discussions)

c: counter arguments (Arguments that contradict the issue under discussion)

The disconfirmation bias hypothesis predicts that the extra time spend for evaluation is used for seeking and finding flaws in incongruent arguments, which in turn should create or reinforce an argument rating bias. The rating bias is operationalized as the difference in averaged ratings between pro and counterarguments (Formula 2).² The rating bias is positive when participants rate pro-arguments in more positive ways. Again, for motivated reasoners, I expect a positive correlation of the rating bias with prior attitudes, meaning when they are in favor of the topic under discussion, the ratings for pro arguments are higher than the ratings for counter arguments. And most importantly, the rating bias is most pronounced for participants with pronounced time bias, meaning that both biases are positively correlated.

¹ Resulting time variable is logarithmized in order to diminish influence of outliers in terms of reflection time (e.g. 10, 15 minutes or even longer.)

² Participants could rate the postings on a scale of -2, -1, 0, +1 and +2.

Formula 2: rating bias

$$\text{rating bias} = \sum_{i=0}^{N_p} \frac{r_{i,p}}{N_p} - \sum_{j=0}^{N_c} \frac{r_{j,c}}{N_c}$$

r: argument ratings

p: pro arguments (Arguments that supports the issue under discussions)

c: counter arguments (Arguments that contradict the issue under discussion)

The next measure, the reading bias, relates to the confirmation bias hypothesis and measures the difference in the numbers of pro arguments and counter-arguments read (Formula 3). My hypothesis predict that the reading bias positively correlates with the prior attitude as well as with the other biases discussed above.³ Motivated reasoners reveal a tendency to seek and read ideologically congruent arguments.

Formula 3: reading bias

$$\text{reading bias} = \frac{N_{r,p}}{N_{r,\text{total}}} - \frac{N_{r,c}}{N_{r,\text{total}}}$$

r.total: all read arguments

r.p: read pro arguments (Arguments that supports the issue under discussions)

r.c: read counter arguments (Arguments that contradict the issue under discussion)

Data

The discussion data used for assessing the three hypotheses stem from four online discussions conducted in three field-experiments between 2015 and 2016 in Switzerland and Germany (Table 16). After pooling, the dataset contains 719 observations. The pooling of data is recommended, not the least because of the low density of activity pattern in asynchronous discussions. In online forums the vast majority of participants typically tend to refrain from active participation (Rafaeli, Ravid, & Soroka, 2004). In the discussions under analysis, only about a third of participants participated, i.e. that they not only read but also rated multiple arguments.⁴ Furthermore, because motivate reasoning theory does not allow to make predictions for participants without initial attitude, participants reporting that they are yet undecided or too uninformed must be omitted from the analysis. And finally, in one of the field experiments, only a small sample of participants volunteered to complete the accompanying surveys.

The four discussion groups discussed about two distinct topics. One of the discussion topics (Discussion group I, II and III) was the Swiss direct-democratic initiative launched by the right

³ Bevor expanding, participants were able to read the argument title and the first six words of the argument. This short teaser is in most cases enough information to guess which attitude the posting defends.

⁴ Not all arguments could be coded in terms of supporting or contradicting the issue under discussion. As explained below, the measurement of motivated reasoning requires that arguments from both sides must be read and rated.

wing Swiss People's Party (SVP). The *Expulsion Enforcement Initiative* ("Durchsetzungsinitiative") was following in the wake of the highly controversial *Expulsion Initiative*. It mandated the government to work out the legal framework for the unconditional deportation of convicted criminals without Swiss nationality. The second discussion topic (Discussion group IV) revolved about citizen' preferences to four democratic models of governance, such as liberal, participatory, deliberative and a technocratic model of governance.⁵

In all but one of the discussion groups (I, II, IV), participants were recruited by an independent research institute. Participants were offered 40 CHF (Experiment I and II) or 30€ (Experiment IV) if they completed two surveys (prior to and after the discussion.) The recruitment method of the third group was different. Here the forum was publicly accessible, so that participants could be invited by email newsletters, university flyers, and social media campaign. It is worth to note that this third discussion just took place shortly before the opening of the polling stations, while all the other events took place when public attention on the topic under discussion was relatively low.⁶

⁵ While for this group for each user four distinct attitudes are measured (one for each governance model), in the dataset stays the model that attracted the most discussion activity. Hence, in the case of 57 participants, the direct democracy model is used. The other users mainly discussed the Representative Democracy Model (9x), Participatory Democracy (8x), and Expertocracy (2x).

⁶ Not only the public field-experiment but also the other cases, the body of active participants was biased regarding political interest and internet affinity. The distributions of ideological and demographic characteristics (age, political alignment, income, and education), on the other hand, were more representative of the Swiss population.

Table 1: Pooled datasets

	I (April 2015)	II (April 2015)	III (February 2016)	IV (April 2016)
Topic	----- Expulsion of Criminal Migrants ----- -			Models of Democratic Governance.
Publicity	----- Private ----- ---		Public	Private
Recruitment	----- Agency ----- ---		Public recruitment by newsletter and Social media.	Agency
AI-Facilitator	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Duration of discussion	----- 10 days -----		----- 14 days -----	
Number of entered arguments	286	90	178	117
Ps with enough read arguments	80	52	507	80
Ps with enough rated argument	45	18	140	38
Ps meeting all requirements: ¹	40	14	25	30

¹ These are the participants that were not indifferent at T1, participated adequately such that reading, time, and rating biases could be calculated, and submitted posterior survey.

The field experiments were performed on the argument tree software “smartopinion” (Wyss and Beste 2017). Argument trees stand for discussions in a hierarchical structure starting with *broader topical aspects* to subordinated *specific arguments and effects* (Gürkan, Iandoli, Klein, & Zollo, 2010). In the discussion about the handling of criminal migrants, a user might introduce a new discussion topic by asking about the empirical significance of criminal foreigners: “Shall criminal migrants be expelled?” Participants then break down the topics into subunits, e.g. how to deal with hardship cases and to which extent Switzerland is bound to international law.

Three of the four discussion groups comprised an artificial facilitator—that is a human-like avatar (reference omitted). The facilitator’s main task was to enhance and sustain argumentative exchange between participants with distinct points of views, i.e. continuously encouraging participants to examine and express arguments. The intention was to address participants with customized interventions, trying to stimulate participation and interaction loops. More information on the discussion tool is provided in the appendix (Page 22).

Upon their first login, participants were shown a brief introduction how to use the online forum. They were also able to access a support chat in case of questions or technical difficulties. Prior to the discussion, they were asked to fill out the pre-discussion survey. During the online discussion, participants received one or two email reminders to stimulate re-logins. After ten or 14 days, the online forum was closed and participants were invited to complete post-discussion survey.

Results

Tracking Down Motivated Reasoning

Whether the first part of the disconfirmation bias hypothesis (H1) holds, can be assessed in the first model (Model Ia) showed in Table 17. It reveals, most importantly, that the effect of the prior attitude dummy is strongly positive and significant, meaning that people in favor of the topic under discussion reveal a positive time bias (i.e. spend more time on reflecting counterarguments,) whereas people in dissent with the topic reveal a negative time bias (i.e. spend more reflection time on the pro arguments.) This finding confirms the prevalence of a disconfirmation bias during forum activity.

The second part of the disconfirmation hypothesis (H2) can be assessed in the second model showed in the same table (Table 17). There is a negative effect of reflection time on argument ratings. People who spend disproportionally time for evaluating incongruent arguments also reveal a more pronounced rating bias. This observation holds even when controlled for prior attitudes. This supports the notion that participants who spend less time in evaluating pro-arguments also give a better rating.

To assess the confirmation bias hypothesis (H3), model III is indicative (same table). As predicted, motivated reasoning operationalized as confirmation bias is relevant also in asynchronous forums. The reading patterns mirrors participant’s attitudes, such as participants open (more concretely: expand) postings from that they can expect attitudinal congruency.

All these results are replicated by argument level analysis reported in the appendix (Table 9-11). The reported model estimate influence on attitude congruence on participant’s reading, reflecting and rating decisions. The models additionally reveal that the pattern seems to be consistent over all discussion groups, albeit with following exceptions: In the case of discussion group II (the discussion group without artificial facilitation and the group with lowest level of

interaction,) all the coefficients indicative of the cognitive biases were positive but insignificant. In discussion group IV, only the coefficient in the time bias model was insignificant, but also positive (Table 24). In it also worth noting that argument ratings are affected additionally by argument length (positively) and attitude strength (negatively).

Table 2 Mixed effect model assessing two causal mechanisms of motivated reasoning

	(Ia) Time bias	(Ib) Rating Bias	(II) Reading Bias
time bias		0.166** (0.077)	
prior attitude	0.060*** (0.019)	0.443*** (0.024)	0.005** (0.002)
age	0.005 (0.005)	0.010* (0.006)	-0.0005 (0.0004)
female	-0.021 (0.188)	-0.450** (0.222)	-0.026 (0.017)
Constant	0.081 (0.258)	-0.762* (0.636)	-0.032 (0.034)
Observations	239	239	716
Log Likelihood	-385	-426	175
BIC	804	891	-311

*The three models are hierarchical two-level models entailing random intercepts for discussion groups. Note: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$*

It comes with no surprise that the calculated reading, rating and time biases all correlate with participant's attitudes (Appendix: Table 23). However, notice that the strong correlation (Pearson's r of 0.75***) of the rating bias with prior attitude is not only to explain by motivated reasoning, as it can also be caused by common backdoor variables (such as participants tolerance against migrants). I claim, in contrast, that the other two biases are valid indicators for motivated reasoning.

Antecedents and Consequences of Motivated Reasoning

For the next analyses, I create a dummy variable whether participants were engaged in motivated reasoning or not. Regarding the reading bias, only 45% (303 out of 681 coded participants that indicated a prior attitude) are motivated reasoners. In contrast, 59% (134 of 229) are motivated reasoners, when measured by the time bias. Table 18 provides the statistics for each discussion group. One result is eye catching: Motivated reasoning is least pronounced in the discussion group II, in which only 30% (respectively 41%) of the participants were motivated reasoners.

Table 3: Prevalence of Motivated Reasoners per Discussion Groups

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
I – 2015 (Migrants-AI)	N: 80	43%	N: 45	60%
II – 2015 (Migrants-Control)	N: 52	30%	N: 18	41%
III – 2016 (Migrants-Public Event)	N: 507	46%	N: 140	58%
IV – 2016 (Governance Models)	N: 80	46%	N: 38	68%

Taber and colleagues claim that not all people engage equally in motivated reasoning. They predict that people with strong attitudes and profound political knowledge perform motivated reasoning most extensively, as they have more to defend and possess greater ammunition with which to counterargue (Taber & Lodge, 2006, p. 757). Their findings can be partially replicated in Table 4: Among motivated reasoners (regarding the reading bias) have stronger prior attitudes. However, topic knowledge (as measured here by a five-item quiz) seems not to correlate with motivated reasoning. Moreover, it is certainly of interest that the three discussion groups featuring the artificial facilitator featured a prevalence of motivated reasoners that is 16% (reading bias) and 19% (time bias) higher than the group without artificial facilitation. In addition, there seems to be no significant effect of the other context variables topic (expulsion of criminal migrants) or whether the event was public.

Table 4: Difference in Proportions of Motivated Reasoners between Participant Groups

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
strong prior attitude	N: 678	0.11 **	N: 227	- 0.09
higher quiz score	N: 181	-0.06	N: 93	- 0.08
higher political interest	N: 233	0	N: 118	0.03
higher education	N: 227	-0.02	N: 115	0.13
female	N: 681	0.03	N: 229	0.01
higher age	N: 648	0.09 **	N: 223	0
AI-facilitator	N: 681	0.16 **	N: 229	0.19
topic: criminal migrants	N: 681	-0.01	N: 229	- 0.11
public event	N: 681	0.06	N: 229	- 0.01

The table displays the p-values of two-sided proportion tests indicative for the effect of the dichotomous antecedent variable on the propensity of motivated reasoners.

Finally, it is crucial to investigate whether motivated reasoning triggers attitude polarization. This question can be answered by using the data gathered in the ex-post survey. I estimate a linear model in which I regress shifts in attitude extremity on the motivated reasoning dummies. Before that, it is important to note that in none of the four discussions groups a polarization trend took place, meaning that in all the groups more people moderated their attitude rather than polarized them. From the 381 participants that indicated a posterior attitude, 140 participants (37%) moderated and 67 participants (18%) polarized their attitudes during discussion time.

Table 5 Mixed effect model assessing effect of motivated reasoning on polarization

	<i>Y=Attitude shifts towards the extremes</i>		
	<i>(I)</i>	<i>(II)</i>	<i>(III)</i>
All Reasoners	0.304***		
congruent rating bias	(0.095)		
Motivated Reasoners		0.267	
congruent reading bias		(0.796)	
congruent time bias			0.022 (0.109)
age	0.007 (0.008)	0.012* (0.007)	0.010 (0.009)
female	-0.012 (0.330)	-0.249 (0.248)	-0.097 (0.349)
Constant	-1.105*** (0.502)	-1.000*** (0.408)	-0.823 (0.518)
Observations	109	193	109
Log Likelihood	-199	-358	-204
BIC	427	748	436

*Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01*

Table 20 reports a model estimating the influence of time, reading, and rating bias on attitude polarization. The table reveals that only rating bias (the rating-gap between pro and counter arguments) affects attitude polarization. Based on this finding, the possibility remains that participants updated their attitudes on the grounds of encountered arguments either by motivated reasoning or systematic reasoning. Yet, the insignificant coefficients for time bias and reading bias suggest that motivated reasoning had no significant impact on attitude polarization. The people engaging in motivated reasoning seems to have a similar inclination for polarization than the other participants.

The irrelevance of cognitive biases regarding polarization trends is visible again in the bivariate statistics reported in Table 21, further clarifying that motivated reasoning neither induces polarization nor prevents moderation. For both, motivated reasoners and the rest of the groups, moderating and polarizing tendencies are equal. The result is traceable in three of the four discussion groups (Appendix). Only for the second group (the group without artificial facilitation) a link between motivated reasoning (time bias) and attitude shifts (towards extremes) can be detected (Appendix: Table 28). Yet, the reported model entails a very low number of observations (N=14).

Table 6: Difference in Consequence Variables

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 193	0.24	N: 109	0.1
has polarized (dummy)	N: 193	-0.08	N: 109	0.04
has moderated (dummy)	N: 193	-0.04	N: 109	-0.07
abs. attitude shift	N: 193	-0.35 *	N: 109	-0.07
quiz score improvement	N: 144	0.03	N: 84	-0.22
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 681	0.25 ***	N: 229	0.1 **
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 681	0.09 ***	N: 229	0.08
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 681	0.11 ***	N: 229	0.21 ***

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Finally, Table 21 displays that motivated reasoners experienced a smaller absolute attitude shift between the T1 and T2-surveys than non-motivated reasoners. This implies that attitudes of motivated reasoners are less accessible by online discussions. Second, there is a strong link between motivated reasoning and the motivation to participate. No matter whether participation is understood in the passive sense (reading) or actively (rating and adding arguments), there is a significant interplay with motivated reasoning.

Discussion

In the pooled data of four online discussions, I find that motivated reasoning is a widespread (but not dominant) mode of reasoning in online discussions. Particularly, I find that 59% of the participants reveal a time bias (a disconfirmation bias) and 45% of them a reading bias (a confirmation bias), meaning that they spend more time reflecting on attitudinal incongruent postings and are inclined to read congruent postings. These findings come with no surprise, since both biases are among the most frequently analyzed cognitive biases and they proved to be influential in many distinct contexts.

Yet, this study draws a more positive picture of motivated reasoning than many previous analyses. First, motivated reasoning (operationalized as both time bias and disconfirmation bias) is not a good predictor for attitude polarization, which contradicts the fourth hypothesis of this paper. However, this finding aligns with the argumentative theory of reasoning stressing that a collective context is capable to level effects of individual's cognitive biases. While participants, indeed, seek for congruent information, they are, however, responsive to incongruent arguments, preventing them from polarization (Mercier and Sperber 2011). As such behavior might facilitate well-balanced reflection, it also ties with above finding that motivated reasoners less frequently adapt their attitudes—whether towards extreme nor moderate positions (Table 21).

The second aspect that gives motivated reasoning a more positive spin is the fact that motivated reasoners have higher activity patterns (in terms of reading, rating and posting activities). Motivated reasoners are disproportionately active, which raises the question whether the motive to obtain an accurate attitude can ever be as strong as the motive to defend own attitudes. Or, by drawing on Mercier and Landemore, when people do not defend their positions as enthusiastically as motivated reasoners, can we be sure that this is done by somebody else with same enthusiasm? Landemore and Mercier stress that “if an opinion is held by someone taking part in a discussion but not expressed, or if arguments for this opinion are expressed but not evaluated by others, or if arguments are evaluated but not addressed, then this opinion will not genuinely be part of the deliberation.” (Mercier & Landemore, 2012, p. 247). Motivated reasoning seems to be a crucial impetus that enhances chances that arguments are expressed, evaluated and addressed in group discussions and thus become a chance to influence attitude formation.

While scholars acknowledge that face-to-face discussions might alleviate cognitive biases, the capacity of online discussions to do the same has not been explored hitherto. In this regard, this study offers some promising findings. Yet, to which extent the result was triggered by the artificial facilitator present in three of the four discussion groups remains unclear. Indicative for facilitator's effect is the observation that the only group without artificial facilitation yielded the lowest prevalence of motivated reasoners but simultaneously featured a significant link between cognitive biases and attitude polarization. This suggests that stimulated argumentative

exchange in the artificial facilitation groups (reference omitted) may contribute to reduce the effects of cognitive biases (see Appendix, Table 28,).

While the patterns found in the four asynchronous discussions provide empirical support for argumentative theory of reasoning, the study certainly has several limitations. First, it is not based on lab-experiments and, therefore, suffers from uncontrolled influences and participation biases. For instance, the activity patterns in the asynchronous forums were highly uneven so that many observations had to be excluded. Hence, the findings are mostly indicative for participants with a certain proclivity to discuss politics in online forums. In the sample people with high interest in politics and with inclination for Internet applications are overrepresented. Furthermore, no control could be applied for what participants have done during the two weeks of discussion. Another important limitation concerns the findings regarding the attitudinal shifts. The data offers no information, whether participants would have polarized when the online discussion would have been extended or intensified. Polarization is most likely, when cognitive biases work continuously over a longer time.

Conclusion

By pooling data from four field experiments, the study analyzes the role of cognitive biases in asynchronous forums. Drawing from Taber and Lodge (2005), motivated reasoners are considered as participants who prefer to read attitudinal congruent arguments (a confirmation bias) but spend more time examining the incongruent arguments (a disconfirmation bias). The study finds that about the half of participants engage in motivated reasoning. But that motivated reasoning does not affect attitude polarization. Furthermore, it correlates strongly with forum activity. While heterogenous and interactive discussions alleviate negative effects, the pursuit of defending own attitudes seems to be the main driver for political participation in online forums.

References

- Bicchieri, C., & Lev-On, a. (2007). Computer-mediated communication and cooperation in social dilemmas: an experimental analysis. *Politics, Philosophy & Economics*, 6(2), 139–168. <http://doi.org/10.1177/1470594X07077267>
- Bodenhausen, G. V, & Macrae, C. N. (1998). Stereotype activation and inhibition. In R. S. Wyler (Ed.), *Advances in Social Cognition: Stereotype activation and inhibition* (6th ed., pp. 1–52). London: L. Erlbaum Associates. <http://doi.org/10.4324/9780203763650>
- Bosio, A. C., Graffigna, G., & Lozza, E. (2008). Toward Theory and Technique for Online Focus Groups. In T. Hansson (Ed.), *Handbook of Research on Digital Information Technologies: Innovations, Methods, and Ethical Issues* (p. 191). IGI Global. <http://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59904-970-0.ch014>
- Brendan Nyhan, & Jason Reifler. (2010). *When Corrections Fail: The Persistence of Political Misperceptions* - Springer.
- Buder, J., Schwind, C., Rudat, A., & Bodemer, D. (2015). Selective reading of large online

- forum discussions: The impact of rating visualizations on navigation and learning. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 44, 191–201. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.11.043>
- Chen, P., Housholder, E., Ksiazkiewicz, A., & Sheagley, G. (2014). *Motivated Reasoning, Selective Exposure, and Cognitive Style in Information Search and Attitude Formation. Presented at Midwest Political Science Association, April 3rd-6th, 2014*. Chicago, IL.
- Dahlberg, L. (2001). Computer-mediated communication and the public sphere: A critical analysis. *Journal of Information Technology*, 4(4), 615–633. <http://doi.org/10.1080/13691180110097030>
- Edwards, K., & Smith, E. E. (1996). A disconfirmation bias in the evaluation of arguments. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71(1), 5–24. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.71.1.5>
- Flynn, D. J., Reifler, J., & Nyhan, B. (2016). The Nature and Origins of Misperceptions : Understanding False and Unsupported Beliefs about Politics. *Advances in Political Psychology*, 38(682758), 127–150. <http://doi.org/10.1111/pops.12394>
- Garnham, N. (1993). The Mass Media, Cultural Identity, and the Public Sphere in the Modern World. *Public Culture*, 5(2), 251–265. <http://doi.org/10.1215/08992363-5-2-251>
- Garrett, K. K. (2009). Politically motivated reinforcement seeking: Reframing the selective exposure debate. *Journal of Communication*, 59(4), 676–699. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2009.01452.x>
- Gastil, J., Black, L., & Moscovitz, K. (2008). Ideology, attitude change, and deliberation in small face-to-face groups. *Political Communication*, 25(1), 23–46. <http://doi.org/10.1080/10584600701807836>
- Gerber, M., Bächtiger, A., Fiket, I., Steenbergen, M., Steiner, J., & Bächtiger, A. (2014). Deliberative and non-deliberative persuasion: Mechanisms of opinion formation in EuroPolis Marlène Gerber, André Bächtiger, Irena Fiket, Marco Steenbergen. *European Union Politics*. <http://doi.org/10.1177/1465116514528757>
- Grönlund, K., Herne, K., & Setälä, M. (2015). Does Enclave Deliberation Polarize Opinions? *Political Behavior*, 37(4), 995–1020. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-015-9304-x>
- Gürkan, A., Iandoli, L., Klein, M., & Zollo, G. (2010). Mediating debate through on-line large-scale argumentation: Evidence from the field. *Information Sciences*, 180(19), 3686–3702. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2010.06.011>
- Gutmann, A., & Thompson, D. F. (1996). *Democracy and Disagreement*. *Library Journal* (2nd ed., Vol. 121). Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press.
- Hart, P. S., & Nisbet, E. C. (2012). Boomerang Effects in Science Communication: How Motivated Reasoning and Identity Cues Amplify Opinion Polarization About Climate Mitigation Policies. *Communication Research*, 39(6), 701–723. <http://doi.org/10.1177/0093650211416646>
- Iyengar, S., Luskin, R., & Fishkin, J. (2003). Facilitating informed public opinion: evidence from face-to-face and online deliberative polls. *Annual Meeting of the American ...*, 25. Retrieved from <http://pcl.stanford.edu/common/docs/research/iyengar/2003/facilitating.pdf>
- Janssen, D., & Kies, R. (2005). Online Forums and Deliberative Democracy. *Acta Politica*,

- 40(3), 317–335. <http://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.ap.5500115>
- Johnson, T. J., & Kaye, B. K. (2013). The dark side of the boon? Credibility, selective exposure and the proliferation of online sources of political information. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(4), 1862–1871. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.02.011>
- Johnson, T. J., Zhang, W., & Bichard, S. L. (2011). Voices of Convergence or Conflict? A Path Analysis Investigation of Selective Exposure to Political Websites. *Social Science Computer Review*, 29(4), 449–469. <http://doi.org/10.1177/0894439310379962>
- Karpowitz, C. F., Raphael, C., & Hammond, A. S. (2009). Deliberative Democracy and Inequality: Two Cheers for Enclave Deliberation among the Disempowered. *Politics & Society*, 37(4), 576–615. <http://doi.org/10.1177/0032329209349226>
- Klein, M. (2012). Enabling large-scale deliberation using attention-mediation metrics. *Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW)*. Retrieved from <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10606-012-9156-4>
- Knobloch-Westerwick, S. (2012). Selective Exposure and Reinforcement of Attitudes and Partisanship Before a Presidential Election. *Journal of Communication*, 62(4), 628–642. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2012.01651.x>
- Kogan, N., & Wallach, M. A. (1966). Modification of a judgmental style through group interaction. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 4(2), 165–174. <http://doi.org/10.1037/h0023566>
- Koriat, A., Lichtenstein, S., & Fischhoff, B. (1980). Reasons for confidence. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Learning & Memory*, 6(2), 107–118. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.6.2.107>
- Kunda, Z. (1990). The case for motivated reasoning. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108(3), 480–498. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.108.3.480>
- Landemore, H., & Mercier, H. (2012). Talking it out with others vs. deliberation within and the law of group polarization: Some implications of the argumentative theory of reasoning for deliberative democracy. *Analise Social*, 47(4), 910–934.
- Levendusky, M. S., Druckman, J. N., & McLain, A. (2016). How group discussions create strong attitudes and strong partisans. *Research & Politics*, 3(2), 2053168016645137. <http://doi.org/10.1177/2053168016645137>
- Luskin, R. C., Fishkin, J. S., & Hahn, K. S. (2007). Consensus and Polarization in Small Group Deliberations. In *Annual Meeting of the American Political Science Association*. Chicago, IL.
- Luskin, R. C., O’Flynn, I., Fishkin, J. S., & Russell, D. (2014). Deliberating across deep divides. *Political Studies*, 62(1), 116–135. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9248.2012.01005.x>
- Mendelberg, T. (2002). The Deliberative Citizen: Theory and Evidence. *Political Decision Making, Deliberation and Participation*, 6, 151–193.
- Mercier, H., & Landemore, H. (2012). Reasoning is for arguing: Understanding the successes and failures of deliberation. *Political Psychology*, 33(2), 243–258. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9221.2012.00873.x>
- Mercier, H., & Sperber, D. (2011). Why do humans reason? Arguments for an argumentative theory. *The Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 34(2), 57-74-111.

<http://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X10000968>

- Molden, D. C., & Higgins, E. T. (2005). Motivated Thinking. In K. J. Holyoak & R. G. Morrison (Eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of thinking and reasoning* (pp. 295–317). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Morrell, M. E. (2014). Participant Bias and Success in Deliberative Mini-Publics. In K. Grönlund, A. Bächtiger, & M. Setälä (Eds.), *Deliberative Mini-Publics: Involving Citizens in the Democratic Process* (pp. 225–241). Essex: ECPR Press.
- Moscrop, D. (2015). *Can we deliberate? The challenge of motivated reasoning to autonomous and rational deliberation*. Western Political Science Association Conference April 2-4, 2015. Las Vegas.
- Muhlberger, P. (2013). Political Values, Political Attitudes, and Attitude Polarization in Internet Political Discussion: Political Transformation or Politics As Usual? *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 53(2), 1689–1699. <http://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Mutz, D. C. (2009). Political Psychology and Choice. *The Oxford Handbook of Political Behavior*, (June 2017), 1–21. <http://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199270125.003.0005>
- Nickerson, R. S. (1998). Confirmation bias: A ubiquitous phenomenon in many guises. *Review of General Psychology*, 2(2), 175–220. <http://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.2.2.175>
- Rafaeli, S., Ravid, G., & Soroka, V. (2004). De-lurking in virtual communities: a social communication network approach to measuring the effects of social and cultural capital. *37th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences - 2004*, 0(C), 1–10. <http://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2004.1265478>
- Redlawsk, D. P. (2002). Hot Cognition or Cool Consideration? Testing the Effects of Motivated Reasoning on Political Decision Making. *The Journal of Politics*, 64(4), 1021–1044. <http://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2508.00161>
- Richey, M. (2012). Motivated Reasoning in Political Information Processing: The Death Knell of Deliberative Democracy? *Philosophy of the Social Sciences*, 42(4), 511–542. <http://doi.org/10.1177/0048393111430761>
- Shapiro, R. Y. (2013). Hearing the Opposition: It Starts at the Top. *Critical Review*, 25(2), 226–244. <http://doi.org/10.1080/08913811.2013.843876>
- Sia, C. C.-L., Tan, B. C. Y. B., & Wei, K.-K. K. (2002). Group polarization and computer-mediated communication: Effects of communication cues, social presence, and anonymity. *Information Systems Research*, 13(1), 70–90.
- Slothuus, R., & de Vreese, C. H. (2010). Political Parties, Motivated Reasoning, and Issue Framing Effects. *The Journal of Politics*, 72(3), 630–645. <http://doi.org/10.1017/S002238161000006X>
- Streck, J. M. (2013). Usenet & Democracy. In C. Toulouse & W. Luke, Timothy (Eds.), *The Politics of Cyberspace* (p. 208). London: Routledge.
- Sunstein, C. (2009). *Republic.com 2.0*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. <http://doi.org/papers3://publication/uuid/2D5DD160-94D4-47E3-BAA9-6ABC6A8B7BB6>
- Taber, C. S., Cann, D., & Kucsova, S. (2009). The motivated processing of political arguments.

- Political Behavior*, 31(2), 137–155. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s11109-008-9075-8>
- Taber, C. S., & Lodge, M. (2006). Motivated skepticism in the evaluation of political beliefs. *American Journal of Political Science*, 50(3), 755–769. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5907.2006.00214.x>
- Tetlock, P. E., Skitka, L., & Boettger, R. (1989). Social and cognitive strategies for coping with accountability: conformity, complexity, and bolstering. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57(4), 632–640. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.57.4.632>
- Triantafillidou, A., Yannas, P., Lappas, G., & Kleftodimos, A. (2015). A Comparison of the Effects of Face-to-Face and Online Deliberation on Young Students' Attitudes About Public Opinion Polls. In K. S. & S. A. (Eds.), *E-Democracy – Citizen Rights in the World of the New Computing Paradigms. Communications in Computer and Information Science* (570th ed., pp. 18–32). Springer, Cham. http://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-27164-4_2
- Vinokur, A., & Burnstein, E. (1978). Depolarization of attitudes in groups. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 36(8), 872–885. <http://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.36.8.872>
- Wyss, D., Beste, S. (2017). Artificial facilitation: Promoting collective reasoning within asynchronous discussions. *Journal of Information Technology & Politics* 14(3), 214–231.

Appendix

Artificial Facilitation in the argument tree forum

The aim of the artificial facilitator closely follows the functions emphasized by Landemore and Mercier's (2012) argumentative theory of reasoning. Their theoretical framework supplies clear guidance about the virtues our facilitator should promote for the emergence of collective reasoning. Hence, the facilitator's most salient task is to promote feedback loops between distinct points of views, i.e. continuously encouraging participants to mutually *examine, forming, and expressing arguments*. Hence, the purpose of the facilitator was to address them with customized interventions, which shall enhance virtue of reasoning.

In contrast to alternative approaches (e.g. chat bots), Artificial facilitator was not driven by linguistic analysis (Wyss and Beste 2017). In contrast, it uses the meta data available in argument trees. The hierarchy, typology (Question, answers, opinions, pro-, and contra-arguments), and participants' ratings (degree of acceptance) create a considerable density of meta-data within argument tree discussions. The meta-data enable computers to access and process the semantic structure of discussed content, allowing for the generation of automated and individually customized treatments (interventions) necessary for the proper functioning of the artificial facilitator (reference omitted). For customizing the interventions, the AF employs many forms of available variables and statistics: To name a few, it uses variables such as "type of argument", "average rating", "variance of ratings", "number of positive rating", "number of counter-arguments", "number of positive-rated counter-arguments" and "elapsed time since login". Each user activity triggers the algorithm to perform a check for intervention. The artificial facilitator in a frequency of one to six interventions per one dozen user activities selects from a pool of about 60 intervention phrases. The phrases are all context-sensitive, meaning that they only show up, when specific conditions are met. Moreover, the pool contains various synonym interventions to achieve a more authentic and diversified user-experience. The latter point additionally demands a human-like appearance of the AF (*avatar*). Figure 1 displays how the AF manifests itself for the users. We opted for a female avatar named "Sophie."

Figure 1: The discussion environment featuring the artificial facilitator

The print screen depicts the four main features of the experiment software “smartopinion” (Wyss and Beste 2017): (1) the argument tree, (2) some of the categories of contributions with their colored manifestation in the argument tree and (3) the algorithm and its avatar “Sophie”, interacting with the user. In this example, the AF asks for an evaluation of a counterargument (“Gegen-Argument”, next to the red bar) that has been raised in the user’s attitude (“Meinung”, below the light blue heading).

The print screen (Figure 1) depicts the four main features of the experiment software: (1) the argument tree, (2) some of the categories of contributions with their colored manifestation in the argument tree and (3) the algorithm and its avatar “Sophie”, interacting with the user. In this example, the AF asks for an evaluation of a counterargument (“Gegen-Argument”, next to the red bar) that has been raised in the user’s attitude (“Meinung”, below the light blue heading).

Variable Description

Table 7: Variable Description

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max
prior attitudes	826	-1.821	3.846	-5.000	5.000
posterior attitudes	244	-0.080	3.680	-5.000	5.000
strong prior attitudes (dummy)	826	0.719	0.450	0	1
abs. attitude shift	244	1.029	1.335	0.000	8.000

shift towards extremes	219	-0.452	1.563	-8.000	3.000
rating bias	241	-0.470	2.266	-4.000	4.000
time bias	241	0.240	1.195	-4.469	5.600
reading bias	719	-0.035	0.189	-0.667	0.667
at least one added argument (dummy)	826	0.210	0.407	0	1
at least ten rated arguments (dummy)	826	0.267	0.443	0	1
at least ten read arguments (dummy)	826	0.425	0.495	0	1
prior quiz score	245	3.290	1.400	0	6
learning	193	0.202	1.139	-3	4
political interest	307	4.085	0.875	2.000	5.000
education	301	3.561	1.036	1	5
age	826	49.352	16.208	15	116
female	826	0.254	0.427	0.000	1.000

Histogram of time and reading biases

Figure 2: Distribution of cognitive biases

Correlation Matrix of cognitive biases (undirected)

In general, the calculated reading, rating and time biases correlate with each other as predicted by theory. Furthermore, the biases correlate with prior attitude, suggesting that prior attitude influences participant's discussion patterns. While the correlation of the time bias and the reading bias with prior attitude can be attributed fully to motivated reasoning, the correlation of the rating bias with prior attitude is to a large part caused by common backdoor variables.

Table 8: Correlation of Cognitive Biases

	prior attitude	rating bias	time bias
prior attitude			
rating bias	0.75***		
time bias	0.21***	0.25***	
reading bias	0.16***	0.21**	0.22***

Pearson's r correlation coefficient.

* $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Time bias on the argument level by discussion group

The following models estimating the likelihood that participants spend more than average time reflecting over an argument. The logit-model conditions on whether it the argument is attitudinal congruent or incongruent. Arguments that could not be coded as either congruent or incongruent were excluded.

Table 9: Time bias (Argument level)

	<i>All</i>	<i>Discussion I</i>	<i>Discussion II</i>	<i>Discussion III</i>	<i>Discussion IV</i>
congruent position	-0.362^{***} (0.070)	-0.592^{***} (0.159)	-0.322 (0.298)	-0.347^{***} (0.095)	-0.219 (0.150)
longer argument	0.754 ^{***} (0.071)	0.918 ^{***} (0.158)	1.591 ^{***} (0.306)	0.696 ^{***} (0.097)	0.515 ^{***} (0.165)
age (stdz.)	0.123 [*] (0.066)	-0.151 (0.159)	-0.253 (0.281)	0.156 [*] (0.087)	0.128 (0.138)
female	-0.034 (0.157)	0.192 (0.355)	0.377 (0.512)	-0.030 (0.231)	-0.100 (0.298)
strong prior attitude	-0.269 ^{**} (0.124)	-0.446 (0.330)	0.243 (0.482)	-0.097 (0.244)	-0.481 ^{**} (0.190)
Constant	-0.862 ^{***} (0.125)	-1.550 ^{***} (0.312)	-1.951 ^{***} (0.478)	-0.845 ^{***} (0.239)	-0.520 ^{**} (0.203)
Reading Decisions	4,657	1,107	284	2,349	917
Participants	413	66	36	248	63
Random effects Variance (Discussion)	0.12 (0.35)	0.77 (0.88)	0.73 (0.85)	0.74 (0.86)	0.6 (0.77)
Random effects Variance (Participants)	0.69 (0.83)				
Deviance	5446	1092	308	2865	1132
Log Likelihood	-2,723	-546	-154	-1,433	-566
BIC	5,513	1,141	347	2,919	1,180

Note:

*p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

Rating Bias on the argument level by discussion group

The argument-level model showed in the following Table 25, confirms again that the time spend on argument evaluation is transformed in worse ratings. Straightforward to interpret are also the significant coefficients of congruence (with participant's attitude), argument length, and female. Also, people with stronger attitudes rate arguments more negatively.

Table 10: Negative effect of evaluation time on argument evaluation

	<i>All</i>	<i>Discussion I</i>	<i>Discussion II</i>	<i>Discussion III</i>	<i>Discussion IV</i>
time	-0.258^{***} (0.042)	-0.255^{***} (0.088)	-0.253 (0.188)	-0.199^{***} (0.057)	-0.377^{***} (0.084)
congruent position	1.574 ^{***} (0.038)	1.746 ^{***} (0.073)	0.982 ^{***} (0.165)	2.005 ^{***} (0.054)	0.520 ^{***} (0.078)
longer argument	0.083 ^{**} (0.039)	0.080 (0.072)	0.272 (0.173)	-0.012 (0.054)	0.385 ^{***} (0.088)
age (stdz.)	-0.004 (0.028)	0.035 (0.062)	-0.197 [*] (0.119)	0.006 (0.033)	-0.063 (0.057)
female	0.190 ^{***} (0.067)	0.226 [*] (0.137)	0.199 (0.176)	-0.002 (0.093)	0.209 (0.127)
strong prior attitude	-0.319 ^{***} (0.057)	-0.075 (0.127)	-0.427 ^{**} (0.174)	-0.238 ^{**} (0.097)	-0.163 [*] (0.093)
Constant	-0.082 (0.059)	-0.410 ^{***} (0.123)	0.384 ^{**} (0.185)	-0.426 ^{***} (0.100)	0.680 ^{***} (0.097)
Reading Decisions	4,657	1,107	284	2,349	917
Participants	413	66	36	248	63
Random effects Variance (Discussion)	0.04 (0.16)	0.10 (0.27)	0.00 (0.00)	0.035 (0.14)	0.08 (0.24)
Random effects Variance (Participants)	0.06 (0.19)	-	-	-	-
Residuals	1.6 (1.27)	1.34 (1.16)	1.89 (1.37)	1.64 (1.28)	1.33 (1.15)
Log Likelihood	-7,811	-1,760	-497	-3,943	-1,456
BIC	15,706	3,584	1,044	7,955	2,973

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Reading bias on the argument level by discussion group

The following models estimating the likelihood that a participant opens an argument depending on whether it is attitudinal congruent or incongruent. Arguments that could not be coded as either congruent or incongruent were excluded.

Table 11: Tracking Reading Bias on the argument level by discussion group

	<i>All</i>	<i>Discussion I</i>	<i>Discussion II</i>	<i>Discussion III</i>	<i>Discussion IV</i>
congruent position	0.197^{***} (0.031)	0.140[*] (0.084)	0.014 (0.141)	0.205^{***} (0.040)	0.228^{***} (0.076)
	0.127 ^{***}	0.842 ^{***}	0.174	0.126 ^{***}	-0.509 ^{***}

longer argument	(0.032)	(0.085)	(0.143)	(0.040)	(0.084)
age (stdz.)	-0.004 (0.033)	-0.002 (0.007)	0.337** (0.152)	-0.039 (0.033)	0.022 (0.116)
female	0.040 (0.079)	-0.159 (0.254)	0.065 (0.293)	-0.098 (0.090)	0.006 (0.231)
strong prior attitude	-0.080 (0.063)	0.033 (0.236)	0.269 (0.295)	0.044 (0.101)	0.088 (0.103)
Constant	-0.874*** (0.065)	-1.092*** (0.359)	-0.594** (0.283)	-1.031*** (0.100)	-0.427*** (0.149)
Reading Decisions	19,554	2,998	951	12,148	3,457
Participants	659	79	51	449	80
Random effects Variance (Discussion)	0.20 (0.45)	-	-	-	-
Random effects Variance (Participants)	0.23 (0.48)	0.76 (0.87)	0.6 (0.77)	0.22 (0.46)	0.78 (0.88)
Deviance	24,677	3,686	1,221	15,206	4,337
Log Likelihood	-12,339	-1,843	-611	-7,603	-2,169
BIC	24,756	3,742	1,270	15,273	4,394

Note: The first model is a three-level logit model considering random intercepts for participants and discussion groups. All the other models are two-level logit models. *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Consequences of Motivated Reasoning per Discussion Group

Table 12: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group I)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 59	-0.08	N: 40	-0.35
has polarized (dummy)	N: 59	-0.1	N: 40	-0.08
has moderated (dummy)	N: 59	-0.02	N: 40	-0.07
abs. attitude shift	N: 59	-0.14	N: 40	-0.08
quiz score improvement	N: 59	-0.01	N: 40	0.31
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 79	0.23 **	N: 45	0.2
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 79	0.3 ***	N: 45	0.15
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 79	0.2 *	N: 45	0.37 **

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Table 13: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group II)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 36	0.82	N: 14	1.42 **
has polarized (dummy)	N: 36	-0.11	N: 14	0 (NA)
has moderated (dummy)	N: 36	-0.02	N: 14	-0.42
abs. attitude shift	N: 36	-0.99 **	N: 14	-1.42 **
quiz score improvement	N: 34	0.13	N: 14	-0.92 *
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 50	0.42 ***	N: 17	0.2
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 50	0.18	N: 17	-0.14
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 50	0.54 ***	N: 17	0.21

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables. In this second discussion group, no participants shifted its attitude towards extremes. However, participants with low cognitive biases moderated more than other participants.

Table 14: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group III)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 47	-0.13	N: 25	0.04
has polarized (dummy)	N: 47	-0.13	N: 25	-0.03
has moderated (dummy)	N: 47	0 (NA)	N: 25	0 (NA)
abs. attitude shift	N: 47	-0.13	N: 25	0.04
quiz score improvement	N: 0	(NA) (NA)	N: 0	(NA) (NA)
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 495	0.23 ***	N: 136	0.08 *
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 495	0.06	N: 136	0.07
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 495	0.06 *	N: 136	0.18 **

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Table 15: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group IV)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 51	0.61	N: 30	-0.14
has polarized (dummy)	N: 51	0.02	N: 30	0.22
has moderated (dummy)	N: 51	-0.22	N: 30	0.1
abs. attitude shift	N: 51	-0.54 *	N: 30	0.56
quiz score improvement	N: 51	0.03	N: 30	-0.56
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 57	0.33 ***	N: 31	0.06
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 57	0.09	N: 31	0.31
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 57	0.3 **	N: 31	0.01

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Tables

Table 16: Pooled datasets

	I (April 2015)	II (April 2015)	III (February 2016)	IV (April 2016)
Topic	----- Expulsion of Criminal Migrants ----- -			Models of Democratic Governance.
Publicity	----- Private ----- -		Public	Private
Recruitment	----- Agency ----- --		Public recruitment by newsletter and Social media.	Agency
AI-Facilitator	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Duration of discussion	----- 10 days -----		----- 14 days -----	
Number of entered arguments	286	90	178	117
Ps with enough read arguments	80	52	507	80
Ps with enough rated argument	45	18	140	38
Ps meeting all requirements: ¹	40	14	25	30

¹ These are the participants that were not indifferent at T1, participated adequately such that reading, time, and rating biases could be calculated, and submitted posterior survey.

Table 17 Mixed effect model assessing two causal mechanisms of motivated reasoning

	(Ia) Time bias	(Ib) Rating Bias	(II) Reading Bias
time bias		0.166** (0.077)	
prior attitude	0.060*** (0.019)	0.443*** (0.024)	0.005** (0.002)
age	0.005 (0.005)	0.010* (0.006)	-0.0005 (0.0004)
female	-0.021 (0.188)	-0.450** (0.222)	-0.026 (0.017)
Constant	0.081 (0.258)	-0.762* (0.636)	-0.032 (0.034)
Observations	239	239	716
Log Likelihood	-385	-426	175
BIC	804	891	-311

The three models are hierarchical two-level models entailing random intercepts for discussion groups. Note: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Table 18: Prevalence of Motivated Reasoners per Discussion Groups

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
I – 2015 (Migrants-AI)	N: 80	43%	N: 45	60%
II – 2015 (Migrants-Control)	N: 52	30%	N: 18	41%
III – 2016 (Migrants-Public Event)	N: 507	46%	N: 140	58%
IV – 2016 (Governance Models)	N: 80	46%	N: 38	68%

Table 19: Difference in Proportions of Motivated Reasoners between Participant Groups

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
strong prior attitude	N: 678	0.11 **	N: 227	⁻ 0.09
higher quiz score	N: 181	-0.06	N: 93	⁻ 0.08
higher political interest	N: 233	0	N: 118	0.03
higher education	N: 227	-0.02	N: 115	0.13
female	N: 681	0.03	N: 229	0.01
higher age	N: 648	0.09 **	N: 223	0
AI-facilitator	N: 681	0.16 **	N: 229	0.19
topic: criminal migrants	N: 681	-0.01	N: 229	⁻ 0.11
public event	N: 681	0.06	N: 229	⁻ 0.01

The table displays the p-values of two-sided proportion tests indicative for the effect of the dichotomous antecedent variable on the propensity of motivated reasoners.

Table 20 Mixed effect model assessing effect of motivated reasoning on polarization

	<i>Y=Attitude shifts towards the extremes</i>		
	<i>(I)</i>	<i>(II)</i>	<i>(III)</i>
All Reasoners			
congruent rating bias	0.304*** (0.095)		
Motivated Reasoners			
congruent reading bias		0.267 (0.796)	
congruent time bias			0.022 (0.109)
age	0.007 (0.008)	0.012* (0.007)	0.010 (0.009)
female	-0.012 (0.330)	-0.249 (0.248)	-0.097 (0.349)
Constant	-1.105*** (0.502)	-1.000*** (0.408)	-0.823 (0.518)
Observations	109	193	109
Log Likelihood	-199	-358	-204
BIC	427	748	436

Note: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Table 21: Difference in Consequence Variables

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 193	0.24	N: 109	0.1
has polarized (dummy)	N: 193	-0.08	N: 109	0.04
has moderated (dummy)	N: 193	-0.04	N: 109	-0.07
abs. attitude shift	N: 193	-0.35 *	N: 109	-0.07
quiz score improvement	N: 144	0.03	N: 84	-0.22
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 681	0.25 ***	N: 229	0.1 **
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 681	0.09 ***	N: 229	0.08
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 681	0.11 ***	N: 229	0.21 ***

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Table 22: Variable Description

<i>Statistic</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>St. Dev.</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
prior attitudes	826	-1.821	3.846	-5.000	5.000
posterior attitudes	244	-0.080	3.680	-5.000	5.000
strong prior attitudes (dummy)	826	0.719	0.450	0	1
abs. attitude shift	244	1.029	1.335	0.000	8.000
shift towards extremes	219	-0.452	1.563	-8.000	3.000
rating bias	241	-0.470	2.266	-4.000	4.000
time bias	241	0.240	1.195	-4.469	5.600
reading bias	719	-0.035	0.189	-0.667	0.667
at least one added argument (dummy)	826	0.210	0.407	0	1
at least ten rated arguments (dummy)	826	0.267	0.443	0	1
at least ten read arguments (dummy)	826	0.425	0.495	0	1
prior quiz score	245	3.290	1.400	0	6
learning	193	0.202	1.139	-3	4
political interest	307	4.085	0.875	2.000	5.000
education	301	3.561	1.036	1	5
age	826	49.352	16.208	15	116
female	826	0.254	0.427	0.000	1.000

Table 23: Correlation of Cognitive Biases

	prior attitude	rating bias	time bias
prior attitude			
rating bias	0.75***		
time bias	0.21***	0.25***	
reading bias	0.16***	0.21**	0.22***

Pearson's r correlation coefficient.

** $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$*

Table 24: Time bias (Argument level)

	<i>All</i>	<i>Discussion I</i>	<i>Discussion II</i>	<i>Discussion III</i>	<i>Discussion IV</i>
congruent position	-0.362^{***} (0.070)	-0.592^{***} (0.159)	-0.322 (0.298)	-0.347^{***} (0.095)	-0.219 (0.150)
longer argument	0.754 ^{***} (0.071)	0.918 ^{***} (0.158)	1.591 ^{***} (0.306)	0.696 ^{***} (0.097)	0.515 ^{***} (0.165)
age (stdz.)	0.123 [*] (0.066)	-0.151 (0.159)	-0.253 (0.281)	0.156 [*] (0.087)	0.128 (0.138)
female	-0.034 (0.157)	0.192 (0.355)	0.377 (0.512)	-0.030 (0.231)	-0.100 (0.298)
strong prior attitude	-0.269 ^{**} (0.124)	-0.446 (0.330)	0.243 (0.482)	-0.097 (0.244)	-0.481 ^{**} (0.190)
Constant	-0.862 ^{***} (0.125)	-1.550 ^{***} (0.312)	-1.951 ^{***} (0.478)	-0.845 ^{***} (0.239)	-0.520 ^{**} (0.203)
Reading Decisions	4,657	1,107	284	2,349	917
Participants	413	66	36	248	63
Random effects Variance (Discussion)	0.12 (0.35)	0.77 (0.88)	0.73 (0.85)	0.74 (0.86)	0.6 (0.77)
Random effects Variance (Participants)	0.69 (0.83)				
Deviance	5446	1092	308	2865	1132
Log Likelihood	-2,723	-546	-154	-1,433	-566
BIC	5,513	1,141	347	2,919	1,180

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table 25: Negative effect of evaluation time on argument evaluation

	<i>All</i>	<i>Discussion I</i>	<i>Discussion II</i>	<i>Discussion III</i>	<i>Discussion IV</i>
time	-0.258*** (0.042)	-0.255*** (0.088)	-0.253 (0.188)	-0.199*** (0.057)	-0.377*** (0.084)
congruent position	1.574*** (0.038)	1.746*** (0.073)	0.982*** (0.165)	2.005*** (0.054)	0.520*** (0.078)
longer argument	0.083** (0.039)	0.080 (0.072)	0.272 (0.173)	-0.012 (0.054)	0.385*** (0.088)
age (stdz.)	-0.004 (0.028)	0.035 (0.062)	-0.197* (0.119)	0.006 (0.033)	-0.063 (0.057)
female	0.190*** (0.067)	0.226* (0.137)	0.199 (0.176)	-0.002 (0.093)	0.209 (0.127)
strong prior attitude	-0.319*** (0.057)	-0.075 (0.127)	-0.427** (0.174)	-0.238** (0.097)	-0.163* (0.093)
Constant	-0.082 (0.059)	-0.410*** (0.123)	0.384** (0.185)	-0.426*** (0.100)	0.680*** (0.097)
Reading Decisions	4,657	1,107	284	2,349	917
Participants	413	66	36	248	63
Random effects Variance (Discussion)	0.04 (0.16)	0.10 (0.27)	0.00 (0.00)	0.035 (0.14)	0.08 (0.24)
Random effects Variance (Participants)	0.06 (0.19)	-	-	-	-
Residuals	1.6 (1.27)	1.34 (1.16)	1.89 (1.37)	1.64 (1.28)	1.33 (1.15)
Log Likelihood	-7,811	-1,760	-497	-3,943	-1,456
BIC	15,706	3,584	1,044	7,955	2,973

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table 26: Tracking Reading Bias on the argument level by discussion group

	<i>All</i>	<i>Discussion I</i>	<i>Discussion II</i>	<i>Discussion III</i>	<i>Discussion IV</i>
congruent position	0.197^{***} (0.031)	0.140[*] (0.084)	0.014 (0.141)	0.205^{***} (0.040)	0.228^{***} (0.076)
longer argument	0.127 ^{***} (0.032)	0.842 ^{***} (0.085)	0.174 (0.143)	0.126 ^{***} (0.040)	-0.509 ^{***} (0.084)
age (stdz.)	-0.004 (0.033)	-0.002 (0.007)	0.337 ^{**} (0.152)	-0.039 (0.033)	0.022 (0.116)
female	0.040 (0.079)	-0.159 (0.254)	0.065 (0.293)	-0.098 (0.090)	0.006 (0.231)
strong prior attitude	-0.080 (0.063)	0.033 (0.236)	0.269 (0.295)	0.044 (0.101)	0.088 (0.103)
Constant	-0.874 ^{***} (0.065)	-1.092 ^{***} (0.359)	-0.594 ^{**} (0.283)	-1.031 ^{***} (0.100)	-0.427 ^{***} (0.149)
Reading Decisions	19,554	2,998	951	12,148	3,457
Participants	659	79	51	449	80
Random effects Variance (Discussion)	0.20 (0.45)	-	-	-	-
Random effects Variance (Participants)	0.23 (0.48)	0.76 (0.87)	0.6 (0.77)	0.22 (0.46)	0.78 (0.88)
Deviance	24,677	3,686	1,221	15,206	4,337
Log Likelihood	-12,339	-1,843	-611	-7,603	-2,169
BIC	24,756	3,742	1,270	15,273	4,394

Note: The first model is a three-level logit model considering random intercepts for participants and discussion groups. All the other models are two-level logit models. *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table 27: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group I)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 59	-0.08	N: 40	-0.35
has polarized (dummy)	N: 59	-0.1	N: 40	-0.08
has moderated (dummy)	N: 59	-0.02	N: 40	-0.07
abs. attitude shift	N: 59	-0.14	N: 40	-0.08
quiz score improvement	N: 59	-0.01	N: 40	0.31
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 79	0.23 **	N: 45	0.2
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 79	0.3 ***	N: 45	0.15
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 79	0.2 *	N: 45	0.37 **

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Table 28: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group II)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 36	0.82	N: 14	1.42 **
has polarized (dummy)	N: 36	-0.11	N: 14	0 (NA)
has moderated (dummy)	N: 36	-0.02	N: 14	-0.42
abs. attitude shift	N: 36	-0.99 **	N: 14	-1.42 **
quiz score improvement	N: 34	0.13	N: 14	-0.92 *
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 50	0.42 ***	N: 17	0.2
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 50	0.18	N: 17	-0.14
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 50	0.54 ***	N: 17	0.21

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables. In this second discussion group, no participants shifted its attitude towards extremes. However, participants with low cognitive biases moderated more than other participants.

Table 29: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group III)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 47	-0.13	N: 25	0.04
has polarized (dummy)	N: 47	-0.13	N: 25	-0.03
has moderated (dummy)	N: 47	0 (NA)	N: 25	0 (NA)
abs. attitude shift	N: 47	-0.13	N: 25	0.04
quiz score improvement	N: 0	(NA) (NA)	N: 0	(NA) (NA)
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 495	0.23 ***	N: 136	0.08 *
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 495	0.06	N: 136	0.07
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 495	0.06 *	N: 136	0.18 **

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.

Table 30: Difference in Consequence Variables (Discussion Group IV)

	<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Reading Bias</i>		<i>Motivated Reasoners: Congruent Time Bias</i>	
attitude shift towards extremes (polarization)	N: 51	0.61	N: 30	-0.14
has polarized (dummy)	N: 51	0.02	N: 30	0.22
has moderated (dummy)	N: 51	-0.22	N: 30	0.1
abs. attitude shift	N: 51	-0.54 *	N: 30	0.56
quiz score improvement	N: 51	0.03	N: 30	-0.56
read ten arguments (dummy)	N: 57	0.33 ***	N: 31	0.06
rated ten arguments (dummy)	N: 57	0.09	N: 31	0.31
posted an argument (dummy)	N: 57	0.3 **	N: 31	0.01

The table displays the p-values of two-sided t-tests indicative for the effect of being a motivated reasoner (congruent time bias respectively congruent reading biases) on the listed variables.